

Nanotechnology in Medicine

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Nanotechnology is the science that employs the use of materials which have at least one dimension of nanometric (10^{-9}) scale. Nanomedicine can be defined as the application of nanotechnology for health. It takes the advantage of improved and novel chemical, physical and biological properties of the nanometric materials. The main areas of application of nanomedicine are pharmaceuticals, diagnostics and regenerative medicine.¹

Nano Pharmaceuticals: Nanotechnology offers the advantage of targeted therapy at the diseased tissue which is particularly useful in cancer treatment. Nanoparticles can be used as carries of drugs and have a number of advantages compared to conventional chemotherapy; i) they protect the drug from biodegradation before reaching its target ii) enhance drug absorption into tumors iii) prevent drug interactions with normal cells. Hence they increase the efficacy and decrease the toxicity of the drug along with increased compliance of the patient. Several nanoparticle medicinal products (NMP) are available in the market which enable *passive targeting* through enhanced permeability and targeting'. Tumors have leaky blood vessels as well as impaired lymphatic drainage. This enables the nanocarrier bound cytotoxic drugs to accumulate at the site of action and reduces the side effects. Various nanocarriers in use include liposomes, PEGylated (poly ethylene glycol) liposomes, albumin bound nanoparticles, nanocrystals, micelles and nanotubes. Nanoparticles can also be used for *active targeting*. Molecules that bind to specific receptors on the cancer cells can be attached to the nanoparticles so that they selectively target the cancer cells. A novel technology which employs *nanoshells* can thermally destroy malignant cells in vivo. Nanoshells are designed to absorb light of different wavelengths and generate hyperthermia. The nanoshells are taken up by the cancer via active

targeting. After this near infrared light is applied which is absorbed by the nanoshells creating intense heat inside the tumor and selectively killing the tumor cells without affecting the surrounding healthy tissue. Another similar development is of *targeted magnetic nanoparticles* that has the double advantage of tracing the target cells by MRI and destroying them by hyperthermia. The benefit of nanotechnology can also be taken in the form of *implanted drug delivery devices* (DDD). Ultra small devices or nanopumps can be designed to accurately control the release of therapeutic agents for example insulin. Because of their small size and minimal invasiveness these DDDs can be implanted inside the body including the brain.²

Nano Diagnostics: Nanotechnology in *in vivo diagnostics* enables greater refinement of diagnostic techniques. It leads to high throughput screening, that is, one sample can be tested for numerous diseases or a large number of samples can be screened for one disease. 'Lab-on-a-chip' devices incorporate a number of complex preparations and analytical steps. The *in vivo diagnostics* refers to imaging techniques but also includes the implantable monitoring devices. The goal of application of nanotechnology in *imaging techniques* is to detect the disease at the earliest possible, eventually at a single cell level and also to monitor therapeutic response. Nanoparticle probes provide enhanced signal sensitivity, greater spatial resolution and the capacity to relay information at cellular and molecular level. Monoclonal antibodies which identify specific receptors on cancer cells can be tagged onto nanoparticles of metal oxides which can produce high intensity contrast signals on MRI or CT scans. After injecting, the antibody labelled nanoparticles bind selectively to the cancer cells and effectively light them up for the scanner.³ *Theranostics* is a combination of therapy and diagnostics. The tissue of interest is first imaged by specific targeted nanoparticles. This is followed by delivery of targeted therapy by using the nanoparticles conjugated with a pharmacologically active agent.

Nanotechnology in Regenerative Medicine

Regenerative medicine is the science of producing living and functional tissue in order to repair or replace the tissue lost due to damage, disease, aging or congenital defects. Tissue engineering has undergone great

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progress with the aid of nanotechnology. The behavior of mammalian cells is governed by the signals they receive from the surrounding environment which is made up of nanometric components. Nanotechnology has provided a new perspective to material scientists to produce different types of extracellular matrices which mimic those present in the tissues. Regenerative therapies for vascular, cardiac, bone, cartilage, bladder and brain tissue can be accelerated by the use of nanotechnology. The adult stem cells have a great potential for self repair which can play a vital role in regenerative medicine. Nanotechnology can aid in identifying the signaling systems for this potential of stem cells. The ability to implant a cell free bioactive material which has the intelligence to provide signaling to induce self healing by the patient's own stem cells will have an enormous impact on regenerative medicine⁴.

CONCLUSION

Significant efforts have been directed towards research in nanomedicine since early 2000's. A number of nanodrugs are approved by FDA while many more are in phase II and III trials. As a greater number of products of the pharmaceutical, diagnostic and imaging companies reach the market we will be able to ascertain which applications of nanotechnology can bring an added value in a cost effective manner.

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